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Daddy, Darling: An Interview with Cyril Desbruslais SJ

(Cyril Desbruslais SJ (1940-), a philosopher and playwright has done yeomen service to thousands of young people in and around Pune. He has been teaching philosophy for more than 35 years As he is entering his 80th year, a short interview with him is apt.)

AJRS: Dear Cyril, as you approach 80 years of enriching life, what are the things that you are really grateful for?

Cyril: That's easy. I am most grateful for my vocation to the Society of Jesus in the post-Vatican era, of the Church I love. It had come at a time of great openness, at a time when there was never so much excitement and adventure in being a priest and a Jesuit. The church was so much more lovable and humble that I was freer to go to the youngsters, when I was a Theology student, and be with them as a friend. I founded the SSU in 1972, a youth group open to all cultures and religions, not only for the goody-goodies but where students and workers or broken families and youngsters with an unsavoury reputation

could find acceptance and encouragement to slowly and gradually improve among people who genuinely loved them and had confidence in them - which is still going strong and active! And there was my being graced to be called to be a formator of young Jesuits and other seminarians. In the spirit of the 31st General Congregation of the Society, I volunteered to teach all faith-and-justice related topics and sought to bring in that dimension to all the other subjects I taught. I was immeasurably helped by the SSU and my seminarians and the Jesuits whom I taught to make my philosophical and theological more Christic and human!

AJRS: Any regrets in your life?

Cyril: Any regrets? Well, there was the occasion when I was returning from a Youth Camp, from Bombay to Pune. I was crossing the overbridge and I saw a nameless villager, with his wife and little children, looking lost and confused while everyone passed them by. I did, too, in spite of having Rs 2000 in my pocket, as a contribution to my projects. I was haunted by the expressions of misery and incomprehension on the faces of the two adults and, almost home to Ramwadi, I made my rickshaw my turn to go in search of that desperate looking-family, but they were nowhere to be found on the overbridge or anywhere I searched on Pune station. I filed that in my memory and made that experience motivate me to never pass by any forlorn and confused-appearing family on my path. I felt that I had met Christ alone and forgotten and neglected to respond to him!

AJRS: You have been deeply involved with the youth, learning from them and interacting with them for more than 45 years. How do you evaluate your interactions with them?

Cyril: The SSU and I have been teaching each other some things. In fact, I am busy still teaching them respect to each other's religions and cultures.

Today's youth have more respect for each others' religions and cultures than youth had some 30 or 40 years ago (there are some exceptions, though). And the non-Christians, today in the SSU, are almost as numerous as the Christians (19 and 24 respectively, are dedicated members). But they are slightly better provided. In the beginning, we all used to move around on bicycles, nowadays almost everyone has a motor-bike or scooter. They are on the way to a higher lifestyle than their parents. Of course, not all of them are equally on the same footing. But these ride pillion on their friends' bikes and we all chip in to share in the food and drink. And when they come into their own (with a little help and subsidy from the SSU), they always are there with their contributions to me.

But young people, now, have less time. They have TV, mobile and computers and race around to venues far distant on their mo-bikes. Whereas in the old days, we would all meet almost every day it's rarely we manage to meet each other once a week. Old SSU camps were thronged to about 50-100, but now we can have, if we are lucky, about 20-25 for a maximum of three days, at the most.

Play practices which last daily for about two months require much more commitment and sacrifice than earlier. But the youth are not found wanting.

More come when there are parties or picnics but a considerable number turn out when there are Outreaches (visits to Institutions, Orphanages or such like, where we interact, play games or entertain the inmates).

Inter-religious services, which we have once a month, are well attended. I habitually call God "Daddy Darling", my translation of Jesus' "Abba Father". The Muslims and the Jews (we have a

few!) were, on the whole, not prepared to "take such liberties" with God, though most others were warmed by that appellation. And when recently a few Muslim boys and girls ventured to call him by that name, I felt that a life-time goal was realised!

What I have learned from the youngsters? More tolerance: young people will not practice Jesuit obedience, but get to work with a lot of shilly-shallying. And I have become a better counsellor, especially in the context of boy-girl relationships and petty youthful rivalries!

[Friends and colleagues have presented a Festschrift for Cyril titled, Fully Human and Fully Alive: Essays on Being Human Today in Honour of Dr Cyril Desbruslais SJ, on his birthday, December 21, 2019]

Fully Human and Fully Alive

Anil Thomas CM

Jnana-Deepa Vidyapeeth, Pune

Dr Cyril Desbruslais SJ has done yeomen service to thousands of youths and students of Jnana-Deepa Vidyapeeth and Pune. He was an inspiring teacher, effective mentor and practical philosopher. Through his lectures and plays, he has shaped the destiny of many young men and women.

To honour him on his 80th birthday (DoB: 21 December 1940), some of his friends and colleagues have out this volume. It highlights Cyril's main vision and articulate his insight on life.

He has been fond of quoting repeatedly St Irenaeus of Lyons, "The glory of God is humans fully alive." Throughout his career, he has struggled to bring out the liberative dimension of every ideology, vision and system. He has also tried to make us more human and humane.

One of his most inspiring courses and books is *Philosophy of Liberation*, for which he has taken insights from Theology of Liberation. Through other courses, like "Hunger and Violence," "Philosophy of Technology," "Postmodernity," "Existentialism," and "Ethics," he has striven to radiate a